

ISic2756

I.Sicily inscription 2756

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

epigram

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Hybla Gereatis

Place of origin (modern)

Paternò

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Paternò, private collection

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI332956

1. [— — — — — — — — — —]CE
2. [— — — — — — — —]N vacat
3. vacat
4. [— — — — τὸ] λίβος οἷ Ἄκι-
5. [δος(?) — — Δ]ιοσκόρων
6. [— — — — — —]ΑΛΟΝ vacat
7. [— — — — — —]ΟΥΕΝ μέγα ιο-
8. [— — — — — —]#⁷I ἀμείνο-
9. [νος(?) — — — — — —]CC [—]
10. [— — — — — — — — — —]
11. ΔΕΙ [— —]
12. ΕΛ [— —]
13. Ε#⁷ [— —]
14. [— — —]
- 15.
16. [— — — — —]αν Κύπριν
17. [— — ἔχ(?)]ει φόβον
18. vacat
19. [— — — — —]ς τε χαρεῖσαι

20. [— — — — —] εἰς τέλος ἄγει
21. vacat
22. [— — — — — — — — — —]NTOC
23. [— — — — — — — — — —] IC
24. [— — — — — — — — — —]
- 25.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

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